

Open Free Energy

Annual Report 2024 - 2025

Executive Summary

Open Free Energy provides essential tools for drug discovery and design, supporting free energy calculations that are robust and scalable without commercial license fees. OpenFE bridges a gap in the landscape of free energy simulation software, developing stable, reliable, and openly licensed software. Our Relative Binding Free Energy protocol has been validated on a large, diverse and realistic benchmark set, and shown impressive results.

Why it matters: OpenFE provides real value for far less than the annual subscription costs of leading commercial software packages. OpenFE members ensure the continued availability and progress of OpenFE protocols and tools. With a modest annual investment, our partners drive continued progress in OpenFE directly, while gaining access to a community of related researchers with whom to discuss and work on shared problems.

Progress: OpenFE completed a major benchmarking study this project year, validating the RBFE protocol on both public benchmark sets and private “real-world” targets. We developed new protocols for Absolute Binding Free Energies and the Separated Topologies approach to RBFEs. We added support for custom force field parameters, and made many additional improvements to the user experience.

The road ahead: Our next steps focus on enhancing usability, expanding the domain of applicability, and improving accuracy and performance. The most prominent feedback we have received from our partners is that the software works, but needs to be easier to use. Our highest priority for the coming year is to improve the user experience, while also developing infrastructure to enable high-value features including membrane simulations.

The bottom line: Open Free Energy would not exist without the support of our industry partners. The roadmap described here assumes steady funding over the next year. Of course, loss of support could lead to a reduction in headcount and capacity. On the other hand, a substantial increase in support could enable our project to grow in headcount and make rapid progress on an expanded set of objectives.

Introduction

Open Free Energy provides essential tools for drug discovery and design, enabling free energy calculations that are robust and scalable without commercial license fees. OpenFE's "flagship" protocol makes it not only possible but affordable to calculate relative binding free energies on very large drug discovery campaigns. The protocols and tools we deliver also bridge the gap between innovation and production, enabling advanced users to develop their own protocols and developers to deliver their protocols to users with reliability and scalability.

The Open Free Energy Fund is a pre-competitive consortium fund dedicated to developing and deploying high-quality software tools for free energy calculations to meet the needs of industry users. The Fund operates under the fiscal sponsorship of the Open Molecular Software Foundation, which provides non-profit status and administrative support. This report highlights the most important achievements and outlines the current status of Open Free Energy from August 2024 - July 2025, with an emphasis on the activities funded by the Open Free Energy Fund.

Free energy perturbation calculations, also known as alchemical free energy calculations, offer a rigorous approach to estimating binding affinities through the use of molecular dynamics sampling. Prior to OpenFE's founding, the landscape of tools presented a clear gap: commercial software is easy to use but restrictive, while open-source academic solutions are flexible but often lack the stability and maintenance required for large-scale industry deployment.

Open Free Energy (OpenFE) was created to bridge this gap. We sit at the nexus of academia and industry, developing stable, reliable, and openly licensed software for free energy calculations. Our modular Python framework enables academics to rapidly prototype new methods while providing the robust tools that industry needs to accelerate drug discovery. This ecosystem ensures that the latest advancements from academic research can be seamlessly integrated into real-world pipelines, benefiting the entire community.

Through this work, the OpenFE Fund is fostering a collaborative community and building a powerful software ecosystem to advance the future of drug discovery. Representatives of each partner company that contributes to the Fund form the OpenFE Advisory Board. A group of academic researchers in the field contribute their expertise to the OpenFE Technical Advisory Council. The Fund supports a full-time staff of software developers who drive the project forward to meet the needs of the Advisory board, while also coordinating efforts with academic researchers affiliated with the TAC. The staff develop and maintain several software packages that make up the [OpenFE ecosystem](#), with the **openfe** package containing the main application.

Progress

The reporting year started shortly after the 2024 release of **openfe** v1.0, with partners beginning to use the Relative Binding Free Energy protocol internally. Over the course of the year, the

project made great strides in validating the utility of the software, expanding capabilities, and enhancing usability.

Accomplishments

Industry Benchmarks

OpenFE's overarching priority for the year was to evaluate the performance of our initial Hybrid Topology Relative Binding Free Energy (RBFE) protocol in a collaborative benchmarking effort. The aim was twofold: i) assess the readiness of the **openfe** v1.0 release for production use, ii) teach partners how to use **openfe**. Fifteen companies participated in the study, contributing their own computing resources on target sets both public and private. By the end of July 2025, all participants submitted their results to our team for analysis, and we began drafting a manuscript reporting these results. As of September 2025, the draft manuscript has been circulated to all co-authors and is awaiting feedback and legal review.

From the benchmarking manuscript:

We evaluated the Open Free Energy (OpenFE) RBFE Protocol across both public and blinded private in-house datasets, encompassing over 1,600 ligands in total. For the public dataset, the weighted RMSE across the 58 systems was 1.72 kcal/mol, with 11 of the systems reaching sub-kcal/mol accuracy. For the private dataset, the weighted RMSE across the 37 systems was 2.44 kcal/mol, with only 2 of the systems reaching sub-kcal/mol accuracy. Accuracy varied across systems with no evidence of a systematic failure mode, suggesting that the protocol is robust but sensitive to both the quality of the setup and transformation type. Overall, these benchmark results are encouraging and indicate that OpenFE may be ready for large-scale industrial applications, with an accuracy that approaches that of commercial solutions. While comparison against FEP+ results shows comparable ranking statistics, a gap remains in error statistics, for which we outline possible paths toward improvement. The protocol meets key criteria required for production use in an industrial setting: it shows robust performance, generates reproducible results, and achieves both high throughput and rapid convergence.

This exercise has been well received by our partners, and beyond verifying that the OpenFE RBFE Protocol provides estimates which compete with state-of-the-art methods (e.g. FEP+), also demonstrated that it can be easily deployed with minimal support. This work has also provided us with a wealth of feedback which will help us improve both the science and usability of OpenFE's tools.

New Protocols (ABFEs and SepTop)

OpenFE has two new alchemical protocols in development, Absolute Binding Free Energies (ABFEs) and Separated Topologies (SepTop). ABFEs allow users to simulate the decoupling of a ligand from a complex, offering a direct measure of the binding affinity. SepTop, as described

by [Baumann et al.](#), calculates relative binding free energies through a dual topology scheme where two concurrent ABFEs are run in opposite directions. These protocols will expand OpenFE's domain of applicability, allowing users to tackle new types of scientific problems. For example, unlike the current Hybrid Topology RBE protocol which relies on a conserved core between molecules, both SepTop and ABFEs allow for scaffold hopping. These new protocols will also enable further OpenFE developments through the cross-validation of methodologies. For example, using SepTop we will be able to accurately evaluate and address the impact of dummy atoms on Hybrid Topology transformations.

Both new protocols are currently available in an [experimental branch of openfe](#) and are expected to be included in the next minor release of **openfe**. Some features will not be available at release, notably the ability to handle net charge transformations, for which a fully accurate solution remains a subject of scientific development.

Initial benchmarks (Figure 1) look promising and we are working with interested members of the Advisory Board to evaluate these protocols.

Figure 1: Plots comparing ΔG estimates using the **openfe**'s default HybridTopology RBE Protocol as well as Separated Topologies (SepTop) and Absolute Binding Free Energies (ABFE) for TYK2 and P38. Note that the HybridTopology and SepTop ΔG values are derived using a maximum likelihood estimator, unlike ABFE which directly provides absolute values.

Support for Bespoke Force Field Parameters

OpenFE provides first-class support for the latest developments in OpenFF force fields, and OpenFF “Sage” works well on a wide variety of organic molecules relevant to drug design. However, some projects involving more exotic functional groups may be limited by low force field accuracy. To address these challenging cases, the Open Force Field Initiative provides a tool, “BespokeFit,” for generating custom parameters for the specific chemistry of a target molecule. Working with ASAP-Discovery and the Cole group, we have enabled the ingestion of arbitrary custom OFFXML parameters for small molecule parameterization in OpenFE. This means that custom (or “bespoke”) parameters generated using BespokeFit can now be used in RBE calculations in OpenFE. Initial benchmarks on the protein-ligand benchmarks did not yield significant improvements in binding affinities, although this may be a reflection of OpenFF being well suited to tackle these types of molecules. Work is in progress to publish these results.

See the [BespokeFit cookbook](#) for instructions, and the [February 2025 update slides](#) (starting on slide 20) for more information.

Proof of Concept for Alternative Engines

We released a proof-of-concept protocol that uses GROMACS as the engine to run a “vanilla” MD simulation (with no alchemical transformation). This protocol demonstrates the viability and future development needs towards developing new alchemical protocols that use GROMACS or other MD engines with the OpenFE API. The code is available in a [separate repository](#), with its own documentation. Try out the [tutorial](#) to learn more.

Improved User Experience and Documentation

We continue to improve the user experience of **openfe** in response to feedback, particularly from [the benchmarking project](#).

Some of this work was done by Datryllic, LLC under the terms of a contract with OpenFE. Checkpoint files now take up about $\frac{1}{3}$ as much space as before, removing a common source of frustration among users. We have made many improvements to our [documentation](#), including writing [developer documentation for the gufe architecture](#).

We have also made several new quality-of-life improvements to our command line, specifically the **openfe gather** command. One major improvement involves handling of incomplete or failed simulation results. As of **openfev1.4.0**, these are now handled in a more transparent and intuitive way. You can read more about the [behavior changes](#) on our website.

Performance Improvements

We have improved the speed and performance of the protocols available in **openfe**. We added the ability to run non-cubic periodic boxes, which enables smaller system size. Combined with other optimizations in our simulation settings, such as the replica exchange frequency, we can achieve up to ~ 2x improvements in performance with minimal impact on accuracy for most

systems. These “fast” settings will become the new default settings for the RBEF protocol in an upcoming software release.

We have also been collaborating with experts at NVIDIA and the developers of OpenMM to improve utilization of NVIDIA GPUs. The first outcome of this collaboration, guidance on using the Multi-Process Service to improve performance on simulations of smaller systems, is available as a [blog post](#).

Ongoing Collaborations

Force Field Validation

OpenFE works with other projects in the ecosystem to assure quality and build capacity. In addition to the developments achieved during the reporting period by following the prior year’s annual roadmap, OpenFE has also delivered benchmarks and developed features in support of Open Force Field. We have run RBEF calculations as part of the benchmarking process for OpenFF force field development, including [OpenFF 2.2.1](#) and [2.3.0rc1](#), and for the development of the deep learning charge model that is being released as OpenFF AshGC.

We also delivered new tooling based on our infrastructure to enable OpenFF to perform Solvation Free Energy calculations as part of their force field validation workflow. This tooling will be expanded in the coming months to allow for validation of advanced force field features, including a protein force field and off-site charges.

Large-scale benchmarking infrastructure with Alchemiscale

The Detryllic LLC team (David Dotson and Ian Kenney) have been leading an effort to create a large-scale execution platform for OpenFE simulations on heterogeneous compute resources. Over the last two years, this has enabled over 200,000 free energy calculations, exceeding 1.2 million GPU hours, leveraging resources from the National Research Platform and the Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center. A major accomplishment this year has been the addition of support to use [Folding@Home](#), the world’s largest distributed supercomputer, for certain types of simulations ([non-equilibrium cycling](#)). You can read more about this work on [the alchemiscale website](#).

This collaboration includes and was funded by both ASAP Discovery and the Open Force Field.

Community-contributed developments

Iván Pulido (Chodera Lab, Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center) has been leading an initiative to develop community-contributed OpenFE protocols using OpenMM under [FEFlow](#). This notably includes the creation of a Non-Equilibrium Cycling protocol which is used for [alchemiscale folding@home simulations](#). This year, Ivan has been working on implementing protein mutation relative binding free energies using the FEFLOW non-equilibrium cycling

protocol and [Kartograf](#). This has included some crucial updates to OpenFE tooling (including both Kartograf and utilities methods). His work has been developed in such a way that, once completed, the OpenFE team hopes to be able to incorporate it within the main **openfe** Hybrid Topology protocol.

Publications

[Konnektor: A Framework for Using Graph Theory to Plan Networks for Free Energy Calculations | Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling](#)

[Evaluating the Functional Importance of Conformer-Dependent Atomic Partial Charge Assignment | Journal of Computational Chemistry](#)

[Moldrug algorithm for an automated ligand binding site exploration by 3D aware molecular enumerations | Journal of Cheminformatics](#)

In Preparation

Large-scale collaborative assessment of binding free energy calculations for drug discovery using OpenFE

Evaluating bespoke torsion parameters derived from machine learning interatomic potentials for the prediction of protein-ligand binding free energies

Notable publications evaluating OpenFE by industry partners and TAC members

[Leveraging Alchemical Free Energy Calculations with Accurate Protein Structure Prediction | ChemRxiv |](#)

[Modular and Interoperable Workflows for Benchmarking Alchemical Binding Free Energy Calculation Methodologies | ChemRxiv](#)

Roadmap

Annual Roadmap

The Annual Roadmap directs the efforts supported by the OFE Fund. The project staff prepare these plans by collecting input from the TAC and the Advisory Board, and present them to the Governing Board for approval. For the 2025-2026 roadmap year, we have divided the Roadmap into several objectives in four areas.

Expanded Domain of Applicability

Membrane Support We will add the ability to ingest and simulate pre-equilibrated membrane systems in our OpenMM alchemical protocols. Initial efforts will be limited to AMBER lipid force fields and key lipid types (e.g. POPC).

Improved accuracy

Alchemical dummy atom corrections Improvements to our hybrid topology RBFE protocol will be made to address some of the issues highlighted by [Fleck et al. \(2021\)](#). We will specifically target issues with known solutions, e.g. how we treat 1-4 interactions, while building tools to help us more easily implement complicated or scientifically unclear corrections in the future.

Infrastructure Improvements

Improved system parameterization Updates to the parameterization tools **openfe** uses in its protocols. Aside from reducing maintenance burdens on aging infrastructure, this will allow us more easily to support future OpenFF force field developments, such as dummy atoms. Specifically, we aim to rebuild our tools to better leverage [OpenFF Interchange](#).

User-supplied solvation Updates to our underlying code for parsing inputs (e.g. PDBs) to allow for pre-solvated systems to be directly ingested into OpenFE protocols. This will enable membrane support as well as allow users to more easily chain protocols with external tools. We note that non-water solvents may not be in scope of this work.

Quality Assurance and Usability

Protocol checkpointing and continuations Enable current OpenFE protocols to resume mid-execution. This work will focus on protocol-specific changes necessary to enable this. Combined with work on improved execution, this will pave the way towards enabling this functionality through our CLI.

Improved execution Development of new tooling for running OpenFE simulations. Key improvements include better tracking of simulation states (i.e. running, completed, and failed), better parallelisation of simulations, and simpler file handling. This objective will be completed through a collaboration with the OMSF Ecosystem Infrastructure team (David Swenson and Ethan Holz).

Ecosystem-wide usability improvements

Documentation and user API updates for key OpenFE ecosystem packages including; Lomap, Kartograf, Konnektor, Cinnabar, and openfe-analysis. This aims to make these packages easier to use by non-developers.

Continual benchmarking and validation The OpenFE team will continue to ensure the validity of new tools and ecosystem changes through free energy benchmarks. This will include benchmarking new science generated by our OMSF partners, e.g. new OpenFF force fields.

Lower priorities

In addition to the “must-have” items listed here, the staff and advisory board put together a long list of developments that were deemed “nice-to-have” due to the limited capacity of our existing team. These nice-to-haves include

- New protocols (e.g. protein mutations, non-equilibrium switching, and the alchemical transfer method)
- Support for advanced force field features in development from OpenFF (e.g. new protein force field, and virtual sites)
- Water sampling (e.g. GCMC)
- Improved equilibration
- New features for analysis

If the consortium fund were to grow, either through gaining significant new membership or through current members increasing their level of support, we could expand the team and make rapid progress on this broader set of objectives.

Long-term Perspective

Alchemical free energy methods have firmly entrenched themselves as the gold standard *in silico* approach for calculating binding affinities. In the last few years, the Open Free Energy project has established itself as one of the go-to platforms for computational alchemy, with a growing user community. In fact, it is being adopted by the wider scientific community as the open-source tool for benchmarking when developing new methods. A key example of this adoption in the past year has been the use of OpenFE in the evaluation of new co-folding models, such as [Boltz-2](#), and [Charm Tx's DragonFold](#).

Looking ahead, our goal for the next five years is to make OpenFE the preferred platform to carry out flexible and performant alchemical simulations at scale. Specifically, we aim for OpenFE to be routinely used to calculate affinities for tens of thousands of compounds on a range of pharmaceutically relevant biomolecular system modalities with minimal user intervention. This includes the ability to handle complexities such as bound waters and pKa corrections. Additionally, we seek for OpenFE to become a hub for innovation and new science in free energy calculations, drawing contributions and producing value much greater than what our sponsors put in. Thus, in terms of flexibility, we aim to make it so that OpenFE protocols and workflows can be easily implemented and extended. This will allow members of the community across industry and academia to develop and test new features, contributing back to the ecosystem and accelerating progress.

To achieve this vision, we have aligned our near-term term roadmap objectives to address the following growth areas:

- A. **Broadening the scope of applicability.** We will make it easier for users to apply OpenFE tools to a wider range of scientific endpoints by broadening applicability through new methods (e.g. SepTop and ABFEs) as well as enabling more complex systems (e.g. membrane embedded proteins).
- B. **Improving usability at scale.** Our goal is to enable routine free energy campaigns that scale to tens of thousands of molecules. To achieve this, we are focusing on continually improving our user experience, adding new tools (e.g. our upcoming execution engine Exorcist, and adding the ability to resume simulations) to simplify workflows as well as

making sure that users can leverage our tools as efficiently as possible (e.g. better documentation).

- C. **Enabling extensible protocols.** We are focusing on building modular tools and frameworks to accelerate progress. For example, through our upcoming work on protocol continuation, we will be focusing on refactoring our protocols to make them easier to modify with minimal code adjustments. This will allow members of the community to use the OpenFE API to quickly implement new methods, for example swapping out the simulation sampler in RBFE calculations to enable different types of simulations such as non-equilibrium switching or expanded ensembles.
- D. **Refining accuracy.** We are constantly working on benchmarking and validating our tools to enable us to maintain and refine the accuracy of our tools. We are also working with partner projects such as Open Force Field, to improve the quality of our models and by consequence free energy estimates. Doing this allows us to measure how OpenFE fares across different systems, and identify where adjustments to our protocols (e.g. introducing new sampling methods) will be necessary.

This year's large scale industry-led benchmarking study marks the first step towards our long term goals. We have been able to witness how OpenFE performed in the hands of a large group of users, where things worked and where they didn't. Our results show that we are reaching the accuracy of well-established tools (i.e. FEP+) **out of the box**, without the need to optimize our default behaviour. This gives us confidence that **OpenFE is ready for use in production settings**.

Consortium Status

Members

Company Name	Membership tier
Achira	General Member
Amgen	Supporting Member
AstraZeneca	Supporting Member
Bayer AG	Supporting Member
Biogen	General Member
Boehringer Ingelheim	General Member

Bristol Myers Squibb	Premier Member
Charm Therapeutics	Supporting Member
Confo Therapeutics	Supporting Member
Cresset Biomolecular Discovery	General Member
Deep Origin	Supporting Member
Eli Lilly	General Member
Genentech	General Member
GSK	Premier Member
Janssen Pharmaceutica NV	Premier Member
Merck KGaA	General Member
Neomorph	General Member
Pfizer	Supporting Member

These members comprise the OFEF Advisory Board.

Technical Advisory Committee

The Open Free Energy project is supported by a technical advisory committee consisting of experts in the field of alchemical free energy simulations. The committee consists of the following individuals:

- Oliver Beckstein
- Philip Biggin
- John Chodera
- Zoe Cournia
- Sukrit Singh
- David Mobley
- Bharath Ramsundar
- Michael Shirts
- Jonah Vilseck
- Emilio Gallicchio
- Antonia Mey
- Julien Michel
- Stefan Boresch
- Sereina Riniker

Governance

The Advisory Board held elections in January, 2025 to elect the following representatives to the OFEF governing board:

Representing the Premier Members

- Kaushik Lakkaraju - BMS

- Vytautas Gapsys - Janssen
- Kira Campbell - GSK

Representing the General Members

- Bill Swope - Genentech
- Aniket Magarkar - Boehringer Ingelheim
- Nupur Bansal - Biogen

Representing the Supporting Members

- Joseph Bluck - Bayer

The TAC elected David Mobley to Governing Board, and the Governing Board voted to appoint him Project Director on a voluntary basis.

Personnel

The great majority of the OFE Fund budget goes to supporting the dedicated staff. David Mobley oversees the efforts of the staff in his role as Project Director, with most of the managerial responsibilities devolved to the Project Leadership Team of the Project Manager and Science Lead.

The team structure implies an open role of Infrastructure Lead. Our hiring process in 2024 did not yield any candidates qualified to fill this role. Instead, Irfan Alibay has assumed most of the responsibilities of an Infrastructure Lead and the Leadership Team has been supporting Alyssa Travitz on a growth trajectory to gradually take over these responsibilities as she demonstrates the capability.

Staff

The OFE Fund budget currently supports 5 staff members for a total of 4.5 Full-Time Equivalents. Two of the team members, Alyssa Travitz and Joshua Horton, were hired during the reporting period to fill vacancies left during the previous year. They both started in October 2024.

Name	Role	FTE
James Baggs Eastwood	Project Manager	0.5
Irfan Alibay	Science Lead & Interim Infrastructure Lead	1.0
Alyssa Travitz	Senior Research Software Engineer	1.0

Hannah Baumann	Software Scientist	1.0
Joshua Horton	Software Scientist	1.0

In addition to the OFE Fund-supported roles listed here, Mike Henry's effort as a Research Software Engineer is donated by Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center at 0.5 FTE. Benjamin Ries's effort as a Software Scientist was donated by Boehringer Ingelheim at 0.5 FTE until October of 2024.

The Datryllic LLC team, composed of David Dotson and Ian Kenney, was also hired through a short term 7 month contract from October 2024 through to May 2025. During this period they provided support as product owners for our underlying API as well as training for new members of staff. They were also involved in several key projects, such as the development of developer documentation and performance / data storage improvements for our Hybrid Topology Protocol.

Key Collaborators

Name	Organization	Key projects
David Dotson	Datryllic LLC	gufe (core API), openfe performance / trajectory writing improvements, alchemiscale
Ian Kenney	Datryllic LLC	gufe (core API), openfe performance / trajectory writing improvements, alchemiscale
Ivan Pulido	MSKCC	feflow (experimental work on non-equilibrium cycling protocol and protein mutations)
Jenke Scheen	ASAP Discovery	Bespokefit benchmarking, alchemiscale
Daniel Cole	Newcastle University	Bespokefit benchmarking
Meghan Osato	Mobley lab, University California Irvine	Partial charges, benchmarking
Lily Wang	Open Force Field	Force field benchmarking
Jeffrey Wagner	Open Force Field	Force field benchmarking, joint documentation development

Matt Thompson	Open Force Field	Force field benchmarking, joint documentation development, GROMACS MD protocol
Josh Mitchell	Open Force Field	Force field benchmarking
Chapin Cavender	Open Force Field, University California San Diego	Force field benchmarking, joint documentation development